

MEDICAL SCIENCES

AMPLITUDE-FREQUENCY AND INTEGRAL PARAMETERS OF SKIN BLOOD CIRCULATION IN PATIENTS WITH ROSACEA

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Abstract

The purpose of the work was to determine the amplitude-frequency and integral criteria for assessing the condition of the skin microvasculature in patients with rosacea.

Materials and methods. The total of 57 patients with rosacea (39 women and 18 men) were under observation. Erythematous form of dermatosis was diagnosed in 22 patients, erythematous-papular – in 19 and papulopustular – in 16 individuals. In all patients LDF-examination of lesions was performed. A_{max} , F_{max} , MI, σ , CV in the E , H , M ranges were determined. The control group included 15 healthy individuals.

Results and discussion. It was found that in patients with rosacea, there is a probable increase in A_{max} E and A_{max} M , which was combined with the suppression of A_{max} H . F_{max} E and F_{max} M remained within the control values, and F_{max} H increased. This reflects the amplitude-frequency imbalance. The increase in MI and σ indices was combined with CV inhibition, which illustrates the presence of hyperemic type hemodynamics in patients with rosacea and a decrease in the microvasculature efficiency. The data obtained testify to the development of branched and multi-vector disorders of the skin microvasculature in the observed patients, covering several hemodynamic components. This should be taken into account when choosing the means of therapeutic effect.

Conclusions. 1. Patients with rosacea should be prescribed LDF-examination of lesions to assess the condition of skin microvasculature. 2. LDF-parameters of the dermal blood circulation should be taken into account when choosing the means of therapeutic correction as criteria for the the prescribed treatment efficacy in patients with rosacea. 3. It is expedient to include vasoactive means with a wide range of action to comprehensive therapy of patients with rosacea in order to improve the treatment results.

Keywords: LDF-study, rosacea, clinical forms, microvasculature, blood circulation.

Introduction. Rosacea belongs to the category of common dermatoses, because its population frequency reaches 1.5–10 %; and in the structure of dermatological pathology – 2-8 % [1,5]. Rosacea is characterized by unclear etiology, multifactorial pathogenesis, polymorphism of clinical manifestations, chronic recurrent course, frequent resistance to traditional therapies. Favorite localization of the elements, rash on the face, also leads to a significant negative impact on the quality of life in patients [3, 4].

The priority factors inducing the development of rosacea include: the presence of mites *D. folliculorum*, pathological condition of the gastrointestinal tract, endocrine disorders, immunological imbalance [6, 8, 9]. However, a special place in the pathogenesis of rosacea is given to the impairment of facial skin vascularization. The redistribution of blood flow is slowed down and the venous stasis is formed in the area of the facial vein, which corresponds to the favorite location of the lesions. This also explains frequent involvement of the conjunctiva in the pathological process, which is also located in the above area of vascularization. However, at the same time, the secondary involvement of blood and lymphatic skin vessels in the inflammatory phenomena is assumed.

It is believed that the mechanisms of vascular disorders in such patients, due to various factors, are vari-

able, but not sufficiently elucidated [2,7,10]. The available studies relate mainly to the study of the microcirculatory bed's skin morphological state in rosacea. Its functional capacities remain neglected. In addition, it is very promising to assess the condition of the microcirculatory bed in skin using laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF), which is a modern technology in the field of assessing the circulatory system's functionality, permitting to control the features of vascularization in real time. It is known to be based on the registration of the amplitude-frequency characteristics of the laser beam reflected from blood components, mainly erythrocytes, which move in its direction. Due to the penetration of the beam into the skin to a depth of 1.5 mm, information is obtained about blood circulation in the superficial microvessels. Tissue circulation with LDF is determined, as a rule, in the E , H and M ranges. Superslow oscillations in the E range are due to the rhythmic activity of the capillary endothelium. Waves in the H range (actually vasomotor ones, are rhythmic changes in the diameter of precapillary vessels) reflect active contractions of the precapillary sphincters and are under neurogenic influence. Fluctuations in the M range are related to the functioning of the juxtacapillary "shunt" circulation. Their source is the activity of smooth muscle cells of the vascular wall and precapillary sphincters. The above structural elements constantly respond to changes in intravascular pressure,

i.e., provide the implementation of the so-called myogenic reaction. One of the LDF signal parameters, which integrally characterizes the movement of erythrocytes in the probed volume of tissue, is the microcirculation index (MI). Since the LDF gram is recorded in the monitoring mode, this index reflects the flow of hemoelements for a unit of time through a unit of tissue volume. However, it is quite difficult to unambiguously interpret the MI level. After all, on the one hand, the higher is its value, the more intense is the tissue perfusion. But, on the other hand, the increased MI can be caused by the phenomena of blood stagnation in a venular link of microvasculature. Therefore, the free space among the parameters characterizing the flow of erythrocytes is occupied by the mean-square deviation of MI (σ), i.e., statistically significant fluctuations in the erythrocytes movement velocity. This index reflects the temporary variability of microcirculation or variability in the flow of hemoelements. The ratio between tissue perfusion and the magnitude of its variability is identified as the variation coefficient of MI (CV) [11-13].

The purpose of the work was to determine the amplitude-frequency and integral criteria for assessing the condition of the skin microvasculature in patients with rosacea.

Therefore, LDF-study permits to comprehensively assess the condition of the skin microvasculature in patients with rosacea.

Materials and methods. We observed 57 patients with rosacea (39 women and 18 men) aged 18 to 45 years. The duration of the disease ranged from several months to 16 years. Erythematous form of dermatosis was diagnosed in 22 patients, erythematous-papular – in 19 and papulo-pustular – in 16. The control group included 15 healthy individuals, compared by gender and age. Studies were performed on the lesions in the cheek area with the “BLF 21” device for LDF (produced by “Transonic System Inc.”, USA). With the help of a special fixing device that ensures the immobility of the fiber light guide’s position (otherwise it is possible to register a large number of artifacts), the sensor was installed. Blood flow was recorded for 20-30 minutes. Analysis of LDF-grams was performed using wavelet transform. A_{\max} (maximum oscillation amplitude), F_{\max} (maximum oscillation frequency), MI (microcirculation index), σ (mean-square deviation of MI) and CV (coefficient of MI variation) in the ranges E , H and M were determined.

Results and discussion. It is established that in patients with rosacea, regardless of the pathological process’s clinical course, a probable increase in A_{\max} E is observed. In particular, in the erythematous form of dermatosis, the values reached 0.582 ± 0.019 perf. U (perfusion units); in persons of the control group A_{\max} $E = 0.336 \pm 0.011$ perf. U ($p < 0.05$), with erythematous-papular – A_{\max} $E = 0.601 \pm 0.025$ perf. U ($p < 0.05$) and in papulopustular form – A_{\max} $E = 0.571 \pm 0.007$ perf. U ($p < 0.05$).

A_{\max} H , in contrast, was inhibited and was, respectively, 0.212 ± 0.016 perf. U (in the control group A_{\max} $H = 0.313 \pm 0.010$ perf. U; $p < 0.05$), 0.203 ± 0.018 perf. U ($p < 0.05$) and 0.195 ± 0.023 perf. U ($p < 0.05$). This indicates an increase in the amplitude of oscillations in the

capillary endothelium, which is combined with the suppression of neurogenic effects on the skin microvasculature in the form of a decrease in the amplitude of precapillary sphincters contractions.

A_{\max} M probably increased, reaching 0.634 ± 0.026 perf. U in the erythematous form of dermatosis (in the control group A_{\max} $M = 0.420 \pm 0.017$ perf. U; $p < 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – 0.657 ± 0.034 perf. U ($p < 0.05$) and at papulopustular – 0.612 ± 0.041 perf. U ($p < 0.05$). These data illustrate the increased activity of the juxtacapillary circulation.

Somewhat other processes were recorded in the frequency spectrum of dermal blood circulation oscillations. Thus, F_{\max} E remained within the control values, regardless of the pathological process’s clinical course. With the erythematous form of dermatosis the index made 0.010 ± 0.003 Hz (in persons of the control group F_{\max} $E = 0.014 \pm 0.004$ Hz; $p > 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – 0.017 ± 0.004 Hz ($p > 0.05$) and in papulopustular form – 0.015 ± 0.003 Hz ($p > 0.05$). This reflects the amplitude-frequency imbalance of capillary endothelial oscillations. Probable increase in F_{\max} H in the erythematous form of rosacea to 0.046 ± 0.003 Hz (in the control group F_{\max} $H = 0.027 \pm 0.005$ Hz; $p < 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – up to 0.051 ± 0.005 Hz ($p < 0.05$) and in papulopustular form – up to 0.049 ± 0.003 Hz ($p < 0.05$) reflects the modulating neurogenic effect on vasomotions, because the decrease in the amplitude of precapillary sphincters’ contractions is compensated by an increase in their frequency. Thus, there is a redistribution of the proportion of factors that form the active mechanism of microcirculation. up to 0.051 ± 0.005 Hz ($p < 0.05$) and papulopustular - up to 0.049 ± 0.003 Hz ($p < 0.05$) reflects the modulating neurogenic effect on vasomotor, because the decrease in the amplitude of contractions of the precapillary sphincters is compensated by an increase in their frequency. Thus, there is a redistribution of the specific weight in factors that form the active mechanism of microcirculation.

Changes in F_{\max} M have not been reliably confirmed. The index values in the erythematous form of dermatosis reached 0.126 ± 0.012 Hz (in the control group F_{\max} $M = 0.132 \pm 0.009$ Hz; $p > 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – 0.138 ± 0.007 Hz ($p > 0.05$) and in papules-pustular form – 0.136 ± 0.011 Hz ($p > 0.05$). This proves the uncoordinated nature of the increased juxtacapillary circulation activity, which is only due to an increase in the amplitude of its oscillations.

Determination of integral indices permitted to state the probability of MI growth, which reached 24.32 ± 0.26 perf. U in the erythematous form of dermatosis (in the control group $MI = 6.13 \pm 0.17$ perf. U; $p < 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – 25.08 ± 0.31 perf. U ($p < 0.05$) and in papulopustular form – 23.17 ± 0.40 perf. U ($p < 0.05$). These data indicate an increase in the number of erythrocytes in the skin microvessels. The σ index probably increased, too, amounting in the erythematous form of rosacea to 1.91 ± 0.07 perf. U (in the control group $\sigma = 0.42 \pm 0.05$ perf. U; $p < 0.05$), in erythematous-papular – 1.95 ± 0.08 perf. U ($p < 0.05$) and papulopustular form – 2.03 ± 0.09 perf. U ($p < 0.05$). This proves the stressful state of the regulation mechanisms

of tissue blood circulation in the affected areas. In addition, the increase in both MI and σ indicates the presence of hyperemic type of hemodynamics in such patients. CV in the observed patients, on the contrary, decreased, regardless of the pathological process's clinical course: in the erythematous form of dermatosis – to 7.12 ± 0.15 % (in the control group $CV = 9.14 \pm 0.21$ %; $p < 0.05$), with erythematous-papular – up to 6.95 ± 0.27 % ($p < 0.05$) and with papulopustular form – up to 7.18 ± 0.23 % ($p < 0.05$), reflecting a decrease in the microcirculation efficiency.

Thus, disorders of the skin microvasculature in patients with rosacea are branched and multi-vector in nature, covering several hemodynamic components. This should be taken into account when choosing a means of therapeutic effect.

Conclusions

1. Patients with rosacea should be prescribed LDF examination of lesions to assess the condition of the skin microvasculature.

2. LDF-parameters of the dermal blood circulation should be taken into account when choosing the means of therapeutic correction as criteria for the prescribed treatment efficacy in patients with rosacea.

3. The comprehensive therapy of patients with rosacea, is advisable to include vasoactive drugs with a broad spectrum of action in order to improve treatment outcomes.

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